

Effective Communication Strategies and Community Engagement in Resolving Conflict of Interest between Porgera Landowners and Barrick Ltd Mining Company, Papua New Guinea

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Abstract:- Using Effective Communication Strategies and Community Engagement to Resolve Conflict of Interest between the two parties or any two interdependent parties is a useful nonviolent strategy to solving conflicts. The study aims to identify the factors of the conflict of interest and use effective communication strategies and community engagement to resolve it. This is a qualitative research and the data collected and analyzed were using questionnaires and interviews. While analyzing and addressing the issue, the researchers consider using Effective Communication Strategies in three different communication methods, relevant theories and host community engagement are useful approaches to minimizing the on-going conflict and tries to put both interdependent parties to a win-win situation. In doing, the illegal activities practices by either parties one way or the other to release frustration are considered legal matters which can be publicized and acted upon independently by police and the court of law. The conflict is recommended to be resolved using Collaboration (*host community engagement through providing service*) and Compromise or negotiation (*agreed resolution by all the stake holders*) approach using a designed four stage communication strategy.

Keywords:- Effective Communication Strategies, Community Engagement, Resolve Conflict Resolution, Collaboration, Landowners.

I. INTRODUCTION

Conflict of interest is the issue under focus in this study; therefore, it is important to define what the phrase means. The phrase, conflict of interest is used in this context to describe the situation in which a public official or groups who, contrary to the obligation and absolute duty to act for the benefit of the public or a designated individual, exploits the relationship for personal benefit, as defined by Layers (2012). As it is defined, a conflict of interest can occur at any level from a smaller context, such as a family unit to the wider perspective, such as within corporations or with a company fighting against landowners, as is the fact in this case study of Porgera landowners and Barrick Mining Company in Papua New Guinea. In all cases, conflict is seen as a necessary competition for gaining resources between two individuals or between two groups.

Conflict of interest, therefore, are tribal, cultural or business groups having disagreements or arguments over resources mainly rooted in social, cultural, economic and

political fabrics of their environment. This conflicting situation is created by the groups competing for the scarcity or surplus of the resources which need to benefit both of them. In that scenario, the competitors are responsible people or corporations who are supposed to have benefited from the available resources under pressure. After weighing out the individual rights of the competitors to compete for the resources at hand through documented literature, engage useful interpersonal communication processes, and foster democratic community engagement mechanisms to deal adequately with the situation, the researchers hope to provide guidance on how to avoid violent forms of conflict in PNG in the future.

II. BACKGROUND

The conflict of interests between landowners and the extractive industries (companies) are based upon serious issues in the world today. No intimate interpersonal relationship with the company and host community due to company not being faithful to paying the royalty distribution, relocation and service delivery to the host community while the landowners on the other hand cause problems like illegal mining and disturbing the extracting company having to release frustration. Papua New Guinea is a resource-rich land where foreign companies register to carry-out resource development projects; therefore, landowners and company issues of conflict is prevalent adding fuel to the existing law and order problems.

Conflict of interest between landowners and the Barrick Mining Company at Porgera is extremely serious and causes eyesores to many ordinary Papua New Guineans and international friends who are here and made aware of it. According to EarthRights International (2014), project sites should not become battlefields wherein people lose their lives. Yet, young women and underage girls are raped like as if they are caught while running away from enemies in the battlefields. Yet it is a battle of rights: on one hand, the illegal entrants are breaking into company's premises and stealing precious ores, on the other hand, private security forces acting on behalf of the company behave, in return, as if these people were enemies creates a volatile environment (EarthRights International, p 9).

However, this kind of lawlessness environment is experienced at Papua New Guinea's supposed world-class Porgera Gold Mine under operation by a major mining company, Barrick. Therefore, every attempt to date to minimize the problem by police personnel (through the

barrels of guns) and by mining company (through providing more employment to the eligible people) seems as though unworkable.

According to Amnesty International (2010), the conflict of interests between landowners and the mining companies in the global perspectives after series of studies fall under two major areas of concern: (1) Relocation and (2) Royalty Distribution. The related causes of the conflict of interest are multifaceted in character but it seems that the occurrences of the problem revolve around the two name-tags above. That means that the relocation withholds the problems associated with it like forced eviction, murder or killings, rapes cases, burning and destroying properties without the owners' consent, illegal mining to name a few. Under Royalty disbursement, the problems occur because of lacking in provision of socio-economic services, lacking factual information, communications breakdown or problem, lacking community engagement, reduction in cash compensation payment, violating set agreements, not receiving exact cash royalty payments; all related to the political structures and systems of the society. All the contributing factors or the causes of the conflict of interest named under the two major headings above are the sources where the ideas are collected and discussed in this study.

Porgera is the world-class mining operation in PNG and lots of internal migrants looking for greener pastures form squatter settlements close to the mine area because Porgera is not a big mining town where people can be scattered around. These groups of people are then associated with the landowners who are not attached to created employments, therefore other informal self-reliant activities are undertaken, with groups entering into the SML area to do illegal mining. According to Sali (1996), it can be noted that the movement of people itself into the area is not a problem, but it is the kind of adverse social and economic condition that the migrants are likely to end up in which may induce them to perform deviant behaviors is the real concern. It is the plight of ethnic groups that face adverse socioeconomic conditions which brings a feeling of oneness and vows to stand together and fight against other groups which may be a threat to their existence leads to ethnic conflict.

Communication is another major contributing factor towards the exacerbation of extant of conflicts of interests between the Porgera Landowners and the Barrick Mining Company. Porgera is only a small sub-district in Enga Province that speaks a different dialect mixture of Enga Dialect and Hela Dialect while whole of Enga speaks only one Enga Language, which is determined by their culture that causes a lot of understanding problems (Division of Education, Enga Province (2007)). This sometimes becomes a language barrier to common spoken messages. On the same note the other mediums of communication used are insufficient for the understanding of everyone, which portrays blank picture to them on whatever benefits the company provides, which in turn causes problem within the company and host community's relationship. Therefore, improved interpersonal communication processes, with

corresponding strategies of resolving conflict will be employed to adequately deal with the problem.

III. REASONS BEHIND THE STUDY

According to MiningWatch (Canada), this issue of a conflict of interests between landowners and the mining company was faced initially with the initial developer in the 1990s, the Canada-based Placer Dome or Porgera Joint Venture from the initial production stage. As mentioned above, the conflict started between the initial mine operator, PJV and passed on to the current Barrick Company in 2006, and was based on the two mentioned problem issues of royalty disbursement and resettlement or relocation. Lack of Communication dissemination adds to the list, becomes the third major contributing factor towards causing the conflict of interest between the host community and the mining company.

It was reported by MiningWatch (Canada) on March, 14th 2013 that the death toll rose up to more than 20 as a result of this conflicting issue between the host community and the two Canadian Mining Companies (past and present). According to Amnesty International (reported through ABC News on February 07th, 2014), more than 300 young women and underage girls have been raped, but only two-thirds of the victims are going through the remediation framework for compensation.

Fig. 1: Newspaper article showing report on sexual assault victims to be compensated by miner

This ABC News was verified by Post Courier on Wednesday April 8th, 2015 that eleven victims were currently approved to go through the framework. Relocation during the initial stage was not done properly so the landowners are still residing close to the SML area. The closeness tempted the landowners and the settlers, accompanied by the host community who live with them, to break-and-enter the Company Leased area and do illegal mining.

According to Mining Watch (Canada), Amnesty International, and EarthRights International the forced eviction exercise carried-out in April, 27th 2009 resulted in lots of women being raped and more than 200 houses being burnt down at Wingima and Kulapi villages. The root of this action was proper relocation processes not being carried out earlier. Due to community norms formed under this situation, illegal mining at Porgera has come to be viewed as not a crime of stealing, although it is an illegal activity by entering into someone else's premises. Thus, it is an open activity where people go in numbers of 20s, 50s and 100s into the mine leased area and literally steal the mineral-containing rocks from the company's rock stock file. Such open, defiant entering and stealing like this occurs because of major unaddressed grievances. These are actual happenings where the researchers have been compiling information, one of them is this one so that the public can know and the government and the company can do something about it to calm the situation.

IV. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND QUESTIONS

Following are the empirical research questions used for this study to collect data and find solution to the problem.

- What are the causes of the conflict of interests between the landowners and the Barrick Company?
- Who represents Porgera Landowners and the Barrick Company in communication processes and how can it best be addressed?
- Which medium of mass communication is most useful in the area to disseminate needed information to the public?

V. EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION FOR MANAGING CONFLICT OF INTEREST

According to Robinson, Segal, and Segal (May 2014) effective communication is about more than just exchanging information; it emphasizes more about understanding the emotions behind the information. —Effective communication can improve relationships at home, work place, and in social situations by deepening your connections to others and improving teamwork, decision-making, and problem solving! (Robinson, Segal & Segal, p. 6). It enables us to communicate even negative or difficult messages without creating conflict or destroying trust. According to Robinson, Segal and Segal, effective communication combines a set of skills including nonverbal communication, attentive listening, the ability to manage stress in the moment, and the capacity to recognize and understand our own emotions and those of the person we're communicating with.

Yifan (2014) explains that emotions play an important role in the way we communicate at home and at work places. It's the way we feel, more than the way we think, that motivates us to communicate or to make decisions. The way we react to emotionally driven, nonverbal cues affect both how we understand other people and how they understand yourself. This can result in frustration, misunderstandings, and conflict. When we do not address what is really bothering us, we often become embroiled in petty squabbles.

Effective communication is a need for Porgera landowners and Barrick Company to minimize the on-going problem of violent conflict. These two parties think that physical violence will resolve problems and might bring peace. Employing interpersonal communication more strategically and effectively can resolve, re-build and bring peace to the community. Robinson, Segal, and Segal explain that effective communication helps us better understand a person or situation and enables us to resolve differences, build trust and respect, and create environments where creative ideas, problem solving, affection, and caring can flourish. —As simple as communication seems, much of what we try to communicate to others—and what others try to communicate to us—gets misunderstood, which can cause conflict and frustration in personal and professional relationships (Robinson, Segal & Segal p. 6). You can therefore, better connect and re-build relationships between rebelling tribes through mastering strategic and effective communication.

When people communicate, they focus on what they have to say, but effective communication has less regard on literal talking, it concentrates and focuses more on listening. Engaged listening is more than just understanding the spoken words and the messages imparted or delivered by the communicator. Attentive listening involves understanding the emotions the speaker is intending to deliver to the participants or the ones listening. Remember that when you perform the engaged listening, you will not only better understand the other person you will also make that person feel heard and understood which can help build a stronger, deeper connection between you, [Vertino, K. (September 30, 2014)].

In solving conflict of interest, engaged communication helps you hear the subtle tone of the communicator's voice that tells you how he is intending to express his emotions and feelings. Engaged listening and careful communication —will also help you experience a process that lowers stress and supports physical and emotional well-being, (n.p). It also happens that if the person whom you are speaking to is also performing an engaged listening, it will calm you. If your interacting partners are agitated, attentive and engaged listening will make them feel understood which help to calm them down, [Vertino, K. (September 30, 2014)].

Communication theories such as social exchange theory is flexible as used throughout in interpersonal communication, group communication and mass media and convenient in such situations like in the mining areas to theorize that exchange taking place in the relationship such as exchanging resources for labor and good behaviors from the community can be exchanged for services delivery by the company (Servaes & Malikhao, 2001). These are best ways to maintain the connectedness of the relationship between the company and the landowners.

Servaes and Malikhao also recommended that companies have to dedicate and set up very effective mediums of communication and provide information to the community on a regular basis so that both parties 'concerns are raised without fear.

Therefore, the researchers have recommended all the necessary mediums of communication especially interpersonal communication, group communication and mass media to be used especially in situations where companies dealing with landowners and other third and fourth party dealers and benefiteres (Vancouver Island Health Authority, 2009, 26January). Wood also suggested that issues concerning individuals with large groups and groups with large groups, all levels or mediums of communication can be utilized because there is no restriction so long as some useful communication takes place and the message is disseminated to the rightful people.

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The total population of the whole district of Porgera according to a research carried out by Enga Division of Education (2006) was 33,893. In that study the estimated population surrounding the mining area was 5,500. This figure includes the principal landowners, the mine working community and the settlers surrounding the SML area. The rest from the whole population are living scattered further away from the SML area and around *Mt Kare*-another new mining area, *Hewa-Paiala* sub-district, *Muli-Maip* Sub-center and *Laiagam* sub-district (Department of Education, Enga, 2006).

A combination of cluster randomized and purposeful sampling was used to collect the data. To select the sample population, it is important to apply relevant and appropriate sampling techniques useful for this research (Paul and Sali, 2020). Therefore, the sampling techniques of cluster randomized and purposive were used and applied in this research. There were total of 120 structured and unstructured questionnaires being taken to the study site for the interview. Out of them 20 questionnaires were distributed to the mining employees inside the mining area. Another 30 questionnaires were distributed to the mining employees outside of their residential area. Twenty (20) questionnaires were distributed to the government employees like teachers, nurses and so forth. The remaining 70 questionnaires were completed through one-on-one interviews in households.

Table 1: Showing Interview Schedule and Study Sites

Targeted Villages	Questionnaires Distributed and Interviewed	Comment
Tipinim	3 DAYS	The questionnaires were distributed and interviews were carried out as scheduled here. The completed questionnaires were collected or given upon completion by the responsible respondents.
Karrick Two	3 DAYS	
Paiam Station	3 DAYS	
Suyane	3 DAYS	
Yanjakona	3 DAYS	
Kulapi	3 DAYS	
Panandak	3 DAYS	
Apalak	3 DAYS	

Palys (2001) states *cluster sampling*—is a sampling technique where the population is divided into groups or clusters and then the required information is collected from a simple random sample of the elements within each selected groups or cluster for analysis (p. 2). For reducing the cost and extending the sampling more easily the research employs the Cluster Sampling Technique. Cluster Sampling is situationally convenience for this research because of its function as definition stated below.

Using this sampling technique the researcher tries to directly deal with the principal landowners, the working community and the affected civil society in their 8 targeted villages. Within the villages the researcher deploys the random sampling technique to randomly select 10 percent of houses from each group. Furthermore to it, 2 people from each household male and female were selected and interviewed.

Maxwell (1996) says that the —logic and strength of purposeful sampling lies in the intentional selection of information-rich-cases for an in-depth study. Information-rich cases are areas and people who possess more in-depth information about any one or more of those 8 different sub areas of study that suit the purpose of the study. And Patton terms this approach of sampling as purposeful sampling.

The appropriate and the selected sample size for this study is given below after explaining the processes (techniques) involved in selecting the samples—that is, cluster randomized purposeful sampling. Using this connected sampling technique the researcher grouped the landowners, mining and government workers and settlers into three major groups. Within that the landowners are grouped into their already grouped 8 village groups.

Those groups ‘populations are further selected randomly using the process below.

Landowners are grouped into 8 community groups. Thus, their approximate houses are 30 for each village. 10% of 30 \Rightarrow 3 houses each \times 8 \Rightarrow 24 houses total interviewed. The approximate number of houses for the other two groups: Company Employee Approx. 40 so 10% 4 houses interviewed.

The approximate number of houses for settlers is 50 so 10% of that is \Rightarrow 5 Houses interviewed. Therefore, the total houses interviewed were 33 in all the study sites.

The smallest sampling unit of analysis in the experiment is the individual person from which data was collected. For example, depending on the objectives, experimental units for this survey was divided into 8 villages or targeted sites namely, Tipinim, Karik, Paiam, Suyane Gate, Yanjkona, Kulapi, Panandak and Apalak at Porgera. These are villages (study sites) surrounding the SML area.

VII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

While presenting these results, it discusses and provides some reasoning as to why the results turn out to be presented in this order; the result will be presented first, followed by the discussion for each of the research questions asked.

A. Results on research question one (1) -What are the causes of the conflict of interests between the landowners and the Barrick Company?

The research question one (1) was framed to identify the causes of the conflict of interest between the landowners and Barrick Company. It was revealed that the causes of the conflicts are multifaceted and complicated in character yet they pointed out that royalty payments was one main causes. When asked, 92% respondents agreed that they receive the land royalty payment. The remaining 8% responded that the landowners do not receive the payment.

Fig. 2: Showing Landowners Receiving Royalty Payments

Royalty distribution is one of the major contributing factors through-out the world in the mining centers in causing the conflict of interest between the mining companies and the host communities. Royalty covers many things which benefit the host communities, the host Provinces and the Nations at large.

However, the royalty in this study specifically refers to the cash payments and other few benefits that the Porgera Principal Landowners receive narrowly at Porgera perspective. The Porgerans regard annual cash payments as the only royalty payment so the study focused along that interest because the problems caused are based on that understanding. In other words when the Porgerans do not receive the cash payments on scheduled times they usually feel frustrated so quickly. The Theory of Mind by West and Turner (2008) took a step ahead and addressed this situation by saying that such people who entirely rely on royalty get mad so quickly and cause conflicts without knowing that other benefits also fall into that royalty tag.

In this study, the findings displayed in figure revealed that the cash royalty payment is received by the principal landowners who have their names registered under the Special Mine Lease Area (SMLA) and Land for Mining Purposes (LMP) area. Coordinated Management of Meaning Theory (CMMT) coined by Pearce and Cronen in 1970s addresses similar cases and situations and states that either parties or members of the interactive individuals and groups have mutual or common expectations. If one side's expectations are not met relationships break and conflicts arise as a result. The theory refers to such as this situation as 'relationship context'.

The landowners and other viewers who see that the method or the process of royalty distribution was unreliable and a thread for stealing they started complaining about it. The non-recipients of the royalty benefits were also supporting the landowners in the complain process because they saw that the process was the thread of stealing. Theory of Social Exchange (SET) by Cherry (2000) further explains this situation by stating that social change and stability in relationship takes place when negotiated exchange of words and materials take place between the parties involved. This theory draws the understanding that people involved in the distribution of royalty payment must treat the benefiteres equally as they want to benefit themselves from the payment as agreed.

MiningWatch (Canada) (2012) identified the processes involved in the distribution of the royalty payment according to their initial agreements. That is, Barrick pays the whole package of royalty payment to the National Government through the Mineral Resource Authority (MRA) and from there it is paid to the Mineral Resource Enga (MRE). MRE takes 50% of the total payment and gives the other 50% to the Porgerans. From that 50% PDA receives 5 per cent, SML landowners receive 15 per cent, Children's Trust Fund receives 10 per cent, Porgera Landowners' Association (PLA) receives 12 per cent and Young Adults Association receives the remaining 8 percent (MiningWatch [Canada]).

Crossman (2012) stated that the Rational Choice Theory explains people generally act out of their self-interest and respond to it by taking action of committing crimes after weighing the potential risks against the rewards from what kind of crimes they commit. As such, the theory

views on social and economic behaviors of individuals and groups. The theory focuses on the determinants of the individual choices. The individual choices and the decisions made are viewed by the theory as one way or the other associates and benefit the social and the economic aspect of the individual or the group making the choice.

In order for the individual to make the decision to choose one of the available choice alternatives, s/he has to consider the cost and the benefits of it. Collins (2013) explains in his study of the law-and-order problems in PNG that applying this theory in the law-and-order situations or causing deviant behaviors, one has to understand fully the perceived benefits that encouraged the commission of the crime. Sali (1996) explained further that the theory stated, knowing that the deviant behavior is unaccepted in the ethnic groups or societies and the laws of the country further discourages and punishes those who cause violence and conflicts. Furthermore, Collins stated that the legal system and police at Porgera are extremely weak which encourages people to make such anti-social choices. It is very critical to accept one of the choices, for it is literally against the societies and nations exceptional behavior. Sali added that when —the going gets tough, the tough gets going. In this he meant that when the situations are going out of hand, there should be tougher laws made to calm the situation.

B. Results on research question two (2)–Who represents Porgera Landowners and the Barrick Company in communication processes and how can it best be addressed?

Research question two (2) was drawn to highlight why there is poor communication between the mining company and the surrounding communities, who is responsible for communication between the company and the people and how this can best be addressed.

When asked 11% of the participants said the landowners bring their concerns to the company by themselves while 10% said they were represented by the 23 landowner representatives. Fifteen percent of the total said they were represented by the Porgera Landowners Association while the remaining majority (64%) said they were represented by the community affairs. The findings shown in figure 2 which reveal that the majority of landowners 'queries and grievances are addressed and brought to the attention of the company by the Community Affairs Officers (PR). The other alternative responses on who represents them were; 15% said Landowners Association, 10% said twenty-three landowners representatives and 11% responded as landowners themselves forcefully confront the company.

Fig. 3: Show the responses of the landowners' representations

In the study here, the people said that they were not represented well whether it is through their associations or the community affairs office (PR). The PR office was established by the company to supervise and assesses public attitudes, and maintaining mutual relations and understanding between the mining company and its public. It improves channels of communication and to institute new ways of setting up a two-way flow of information and understanding.

An additional study was convened and other observations reflected that their queries and grievances are addressed by the Community Affairs Officers and then brings to the attention of the company. They said that the representation is usually unfair because the Community Relation Officers are the company's employees. They think about their job being victimized if they talk hard on the company just as the situational aggressive landowners. As a result the community affairs officers do not liaise with the community and the company honestly causing the conflict of interest. Meeting with stakeholders unplanned or doing it because of confrontation is not a good business. As theorized by Effective Group Decision-Making Theory termed by John Oetzel (1995) around 1990s, your intergroup relationship partner is the impact maker to the business.

Also in the finding, the study revealed that the landowners really need to communicate directly to the company when they have queries and grievances along the benefit channel. Eighty-three percent (83%) of the respondents said that they did not have any chance of having face-to-face constructive negotiations ever since the mining started. The remaining minority population said they need not have to face the company for they have their representative who can have conversations on behalf of them. Therefore, in several open interviews government employees and community chiefs talked about landowners' need to have close and regular dialogues with Barrick Company.

According to Rogers (2003), communication is the process by which people (individuals or group) exchange information, feelings, and meaning through verbal and non-verbal messages. Wood (2010) added to Roger's definition of communication by saying that it is a two-way communication process of reaching mutual understanding, in which the receiver and the sender not only exchange

information or feelings but also create and share meaning. Katz (1947) put forward communication in its simplest terms; defined as: it's the art of getting the right information to the right people at the right time in the right format via the right channel.

One way going forward, the people felt that the company should speak to them regularly of what they are doing and how they are benefiting from the production. Just a matter of face-to-face verbal communication can satisfy them too as they testified in interviews.

According to Amnesty International (2010), while signing the agreement for the Porgera mining to take place the stakeholders constitute consensus by saying that while the production proceeds and any violations and issues occur concerning the agreement has to be solved in a no violence face-to-face dialogue. However, reports from daily newspapers and speculations from people are contrary to this contract. According to the World Bank (2010) the Barrick Company needs to engage the civil landowners in regular conversations to brief them on what the company is doing especially on the community developments. The company has done a lot of individual community socioeconomic projects in isolation which make the landowners feel that they are deliberately avoided, leading them to cause some of the disturbances. PNG Mine Watch further stated that the company should engage the community in such a way to make them take ownership of these projects from the start to the end. That is what they are mostly struggling for.

C. Results on research question three (3)- Which medium of mass communication is most useful in the area to disseminate needed information to the public?

The research question three (3) was designed to investigation which medium of communication is most useful in the area to disseminate needed information to the public. When asked, 5% of respondents said Miok FM is available while 11% said EMTV is available for them to publicize any law-and order issues. Thirty-seven percent of the respondents said Ipili FM is readily available while a total of 13% said National News and Post Courier are available at times. However, 34% said no media is available to inform and publicize such information as indicated in the Table 2 below.

Table 2: Availability of Media Services and Uses

Open ended Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Miok FM	5	5 %
EMTV	11	11 %
Ipili FM	37	37 %
Sometimes National Newspaper	6	6%
Sometimes Post Courier	7	7%
No Media Service	34	34%
Total Responses	100	100%

The findings presented in table 2 state that Ipili FM is the only broadcasting audio service readily available at Porgera. The other multimedia and print media services are rarely available. Miok FM is another radio service at the

Provincial level that is available in the provincial town. Print Media services especially the most common ones, National and Post Courier offices are not there. We receive these two daily papers one or two days late at the Provincial town,

Wabag so to Porgera it takes two to three days late. By the time the daily papers arrive at Porgera, they are already outdated. At times when the EMTV signals are high they have access to it, but they do not have an office where people or company can express concerns for public notices and awareness.

The Internet and mobile services are now making the life easy for the people to report any illegal actions against anyone, but people from the area or any area do not have formal connections with the print and multimedia services. Such press releases and public cases are usually untrusted and can be unreliable to be publicized according to the companies' code of ethics unless any employee from the media company personally takes reports and reports it becomes useful.

Mass Communication is a process where individuals, small or large group of people and or organizations send information through a channel of communication to a larger anonymous and heterogeneous audience at the same time (Grimsley, S. (n.d). Channels of communication include broadcast television, radio, social media, and print media. Since the message that someone is sending planned to reach wider range of people, the regular presenter (host) must be trained to be flexible to assisting the information providers in interpreting the message while disseminating if the message provider sends the information directly.

According to Agenda-Setting Theory (AST) by Scheufele, (2000), to solve a problem concerning large group of people through communication, high quality media services must be available and the officers setting the agendas must be free of influence. The salient message must be broadcasted or circulated repeatedly. AST was formally developed by Dr. Max McCombs and Dr. Donald Shaw in a study on the 1968 US Presidential Election (Grimsley, n.d). The theory's great concern was on the salience of topics on the public agenda. The importance is that if news item was repeatedly announced, publicized or covered, it reminds the audience that the issue is of great concern where they have to seriously take into account.

According to Grimsley (n.d), agenda building involves not only active role of media organizations, but also the emphasis was made on public participation and policymakers.

Furthermore, Scheufele (2000, p.4), the difference between —agenda setting and —agenda building are based on the important role of media or public. Therefore, when setting an agenda it could primarily base on the effect of the media agenda where the audiences are, transfer of the media agenda to the public agenda, in doing so the mass media and public media can affect or influence the public policy (Scheufele, p.5). Media services are very essential in such mining centers like Porgera to disseminate vital information like issues affecting people in such major project areas. They are also better mediums for the company to circulate memos and notices for concerned people like the landowner representatives and the whole civil society.

Since the media service is targeted to solve issues and conflict concerning the stakeholders, regulations must be set concerning the usage of the media by all the stakeholders including the landowners through 23 reps, PDA and Porgera Landowners Association, governments and the company in the light of the legal laws of the country so that individual's rights are protected by the media and their rights are also exercised through that media. Thus, the presenters have to be honest and transparent in setting and reporting the agendas knowing that they are playing a great role in resolving the conflict of interest.

VIII. RECOMMENDATIONS

In this section, there are four (4) areas of recommendations. These are; royalty distribution, integrated conflict program, community engagement and active media service.

A. Royalty Distribution

Royalty distribution is one of the core factors contributing towards the conflicting issue between Barrick and the landowners. The studies have stated that the royalty distribution especially the cash compensation and payment do not reach the rightful landowners on the expected time and in the full expected amount. It was also identified that instead of the money directly reaching them from the company, it goes through series of stages which decrease the initial amount as a result. That leads to a lot of conflicts amongst the stakeholders so it is therefore, following points are recommended to alleviate the conflicting issues:

- The royalty payment in cash to the landowners must be made by the company to their individual accounts.
- The payment must be done to them on the exact stated times.
- The amount paid to them must be recorded by the company, the National and
- Provincial governments and the PDA or Landowners' Association offices and report to them the total figure to confirm the exactness and clarity on provided mass media.
- Changes in the amount of payment must be reported to them accordingly and timely on mass media.
- The other forms of benefits and other beneficiaries must be made known to them on regular bases during meetings and mass media.

B. Integrated Conflict Program

The findings have shown that the government agents, company and people were working in isolation. Lack of cooperation among these groups and weakness of the agents and the company provided more chances for opportunists to enter into violence especially illegal mining, killing and rape. Therefore, integrated community management program is recommended to monitor and manage the conflict in the valley. This management program will be an organisation which is recommended to be in operation and function in partnership with the provincial government, police and the courts.

➤ *Functions of Government Agents and the Company*

The company will provide funding, media mechanisms of information transfers, avenues and trainings and other logistics. The government agents with the help of the main governments will provide management, funding and strategize policies to actively combat crime and violence in the Porgera Valley. Other law guides would also be supported for this purpose.

➤ *Members of the Organization*

The members of the organization would comprise the senior officers of the government from the valley like the district administration, Head Teachers and Deputy Head Teachers of Porgera High School and other surrounding Primary schools, Health Services and Police. Senior Executives from the Companies (Barrick and other affiliated companies), LLG Presidents and town councillors, selected community members and professional managers and local researchers. They would conduct meetings according to their schedule times for arranging and organizing work duties and adopting work programs.

➤ *Purpose of the organization*

The purpose of the organization is to provide an effective conflict management program with the aim firstly to investigate the reasons for the conflict of interest between the stakeholders and spell out who is at fault and secondly to minimize the associated law-andorder problems in the mining town. Following are the main functions or program of the organization in order to achieve the goal.

- Monitor every part of the community and make daily reports on any issue identified
- Formulate ideas on adopting possible course of actions on any issue
- Planning and designing awareness programs in the villages and settlements through media
- Conduct regular research work
- Training youths and community leaders
- Recruiting youths for community work programs
- Identify cultural factors of misunderstanding and miscommunications

➤ *Effective communication strategies*

Effective Communication Strategies for Conflict Management described in (4.0) of this paper is the vital mechanism needed to disseminate information and resolve conflicts so it can be taught by an expert as an initial training to the members of the organization so that they become the individual trainers of the trainees. The Shannon's communication models can also be explained to them by the same expert may be from the communication and development studies department. The expert would involve in recruitment and training of youths, conducting research, planning and designing programs, formulating ideas, monitoring and reporting issues and identifying cultural factors of miscommunications. The subject areas for these work programs includes; socio-economic, cultural issues, illegal mining, relocation, royalty distribution, community engagement and religious programs.

C. *Community Engagement*

Involving the host community members in the service planning and service deliver machinery will give more chance to the community as the stakeholder to take ownership of the project and the problems that are happening in Porgera. In doing so, it will start to ease the conflict of interest between the two stakeholders. Therefore, following points are recommended to alleviate the conflict of interest between the stakeholders.

- Company and the government must engage the youths in community projects.
- Engage many of the leader-minded community members in the community project planning and developments machinery.
- Government and the company must organize sports to engage youths to get emerged with the sporting activities.
- Engage more host community members in the employment opportunities provided.
- Engage women and young girls in life-long trainings like sawing and maternal care trainings.
- Subsidize school fees and engage all school age youths in all levels of school.

D. *Active Media Service*

Media service is a fundamental information delivery services that is in operation in such areas that plays a vital role in disseminating useful information to the concerned public. The findings revealed that Porgera Valley does not have print or multimedia services or branches from where they could disseminate their information within Porgera and around Papua New Guinea. The only service they have is Ipili FM primarily used for entertainment purposes which does not have high frequencies. Therefore, to facilitate landowners with informed knowledge, the following points are recommended:

- The governments and Barrick must fund and motivate one of the Print Media Companies to set up a branch at Porgera to disseminate information that will service the whole of Enga Province for the Province does not have one for its life time.
- The governments including Local Level Governments and the Barrick Company must collaboratively improve and fully equip the existing Ipili FM that signals can be received from all through-out PNG so that the information must be delivered fully. Those who cannot afford to use print media service must use the audio service to receive and disseminate the useful information.
- Multimedia service facilities must be improved by the Barrick Company with the help of the governments to receive the EMTV signals to absorb information regarding law and order issues and other necessary information from the governments for the good of the people living at Porgera.

IX. CONCLUSION

This chapter has worked out and presented the fundamental concluding points on how to diminish and resolve the conflict of interest between the landowners and Barrick Company at Porgera Mining area. The vital recommendations to address the conflicting issue between the two stakeholders which lead to the law-and-order problems in the area were discussed under the four (4) useful headings. These includes: Royalty Distribution, Integrated conflict management program, Community Engagement and Active Media Services. These headings are conflict resolving mechanisms where each has to be given very close attention to select the appropriate strategy for implementation by the National Government, Provincial Government and the Barrick Company to address the issue under study.

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